

D5.4

Equality, diversity and inclusion models

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Author(s)	Jon Pizarro, María López
Other Contributors	Lut Mergaert (YW), Xavier Eeckhout (FECYT)
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Information in this report that may influence other GEARING-ROLES tasks

Linked Task	Points of Relevance
Task 5.4	This report will affect all the outcomes and activities of the WP, as all the training initiatives will depend on this planning.

GEARING-ROLES project

GEARING-Roles is a four-year (January 2019 – December 2022) Coordination and Support Action project that brings together a pan-European group of academics and industry professionals to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned on designing, implementing, and evaluating 6 Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The project therefore has a firm objective of challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers and working towards real institutional change. This multidisciplinary, multinational, and multi-sectorial collaboration will be supported by training, mentoring activities, awareness raising campaigns as well as bi-annual videos and podcasts and annual networking events.

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List of Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
HEI	Higher Education Institution
HR	Human Resources
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
WLB	Work-Life Balance
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document is the Design of Training Modules (D5.4) developed under task 5.4 by WP5 leader UDEUSTO. With the aim of providing some tools to enhance the skills and the awareness-raising regarding leadership and decision-making, in the context of WP5 a complete set of training modules have been designed. These training modules are a combination of on-site sessions, webinars and intensive leadership programmes, each of which targets a different audience and tackles a different topic, most of them identified from the Institutional Assessment Reports, in order to achieve a more gender-balanced leadership bodies in GEP implementing institutions.

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1. Introduction

This document is the *Equality, diversity and inclusion models* (D5.4) by WP5 leader University of Deusto.

The general objectives of the WP are focused on two main axes: (i) encourage equal participation of men and women in leadership and decision-making structures, and (ii) support awareness rising through the development of behavioral changes to promote an inclusive leadership.

With these challenges in mind, several initiatives can be programmed in the context of the GEP implementation period, either at an institutional level (as actions informing GEPs) or project level (as specific activities outside GEPs and delivered in the WP5 framework).

From the Desk Research Analysis performed to capture some relevant inspiring practices regarding leadership and decision-making processes (and collated in Deliverable 5.1), we can observe how frequent is the use of training initiatives both to make people (including actual managers and potential candidates) aware of the necessity of gender-balanced bodies and to shape new behaviors and empower female candidates.

The trainings planned in this document are a core part of D5.3: Action Plan and most of them will be delivered during the first and the second year of the project (with the exception of trainings scheduled in the context of Pairing Events).

The structure of this report comprises two different but interconnected sections. In the first section, we include a description of the main gaps in leadership and decision making arising from institutional assessments.

Once these gaps have been identified, the second section includes a complete set of training modules that target directly to cover the key topics that affects either to all the implementing partners (in the case of general activities) or to any of them (for which partner-specific sessions will be used).

Finally, it is important to highlight that the outcomes of the training sessions organized under this Deliverable and the consequent Task 5.4 will be compiled in Deliverable 5.5, where whether the trainings met the expected results or more sessions need to be scheduled for the following years within each GEP implementing institution will be assessed.

2. Issues arising from Institutional Assessment Reports

This section contains a summary of the different issues each GEP implementing institution has identified on their Institutional Assessment Reports. As we are going to address in the following paragraphs, most of the institutions have common challenges in leadership, with some variations due to several factors, such as the national context and the performance of the institution regarding gender equality.

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1. Instituto de Geografia e Ordenamento do Território - IGOT

First, it is important to highlight how statistics on IGOT's Assessment Report show that there are gender imbalances in representation at Faculty level: the three main bodies at IGOT (management council, scientific council and pedagogic council) are men-dominated, with a very low participation rate of women. As for 31/12/2018, the composition of the three bodies was:

	Women	Men
Management Council	0%	100%
Scientific Council	23.1%	76.9%
Pedagogic Council	33.3%	66.7%

In order to a better understanding of the previous numbers, the gender composition of the teaching and research staff at IGOT should be presented, in order to see whether there is a lower possibility of women of accessing management positions. In this sense, IGOT has a 40% of women full professors, and a 42.9% of women associate professors. Consequently, there are lower possibilities for women to access management positions (particularly in the management council, highest decision-making body).

Another aspect that has been identified, mainly in the qualitative data, is the fact that management positions have been offered to women, but they refused to enroll on leadership tasks, without more explanation that a general lack of time/availability. In this sense, a top manager of IGOT stated:

"[...] She was invited after a tender and she wasn't available to undertake collective, institutional positions... but she was a person to whom I spoke about integrating the Centre's management. In fact, she showed no availability and I did not think about the composition of the gender balance [...]"

Finally, IGOT should keep an eye on the lack of awareness about the existence of a gender-related problem at management bodies, which have been expressed by some components of the management bodies. Nevertheless, it is also recognized that a tendency to occupy the management positions with men (bias) exists, but no specific justification is given:

"I also think we do not have, in the first place, a serious gender equality problem. That being said, I am also increasingly sensitive to the relevance of gender equality in the college in general and also in CEG as the decision and coordination positions tend to be occupied by men. Evidently, they must be qualified people, but there are also qualified women and, sometimes, there is a tendency to invite or support more male individuals"

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for certain positions. I don't know why; I don't know if it is because it seems to us that these people are more available or..."

2. Faculty of Arts of University of Ljubljana - UL

Following the general trend of the University of Ljubljana, the Faculty of Arts faces gender imbalances. In this case, the disequilibrium in the top management at Faculty level is clear: in the 2009-2019 period, there have been thirteen male vice-deans versus only five women. At middle management positions, in contrast, there is gender balance, even with more women than men in most of the positions (although this difference falls into 60/40 parity criteria):

	Women	Men
Head of Department	61.9%	38.1%
Service and Research Centres	50%	50%
Senate	54.7%	45.3%

Again, the probability of reaching top management positions (deanery or vice-deanery) is lower for women in a Faculty with a 49% of women professors and only a 27.7% of women vice-deans in a ten-year period.

Beyond the quantitative data mentioned above, the qualitative information compiled reveals a tension between the understanding of gender equality and academic achievements, in the sense that both are perceived as mutually exclusive.

The leadership positions are seen as an additional workload rather than a privilege, making even more difficult the work-life balance (WLB) and the academic career of people appointed to these positions.

Finally, regarding decision-making processes, the size of the faculty and the specificities of the leadership and related processes, are seen as a factor adding more complexity to the procedures and, as a consequence, to the achievement of a gender balance.

3. Oxford Brookes University - OBU

OBU is doing particularly well regarding gender representation at the different management bodies, including a 50% of women in the Vice-Chancellor Group, a 47% in the Academic Board and a 56% in the Research and Knowledge Exchange Committee. However, there are still some men overrepresentations in some top positions, such as the Board of Governors that holds a 38% of women members (while this number was 54% in 2016-17 period).

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In this case, there are not career progression issues, as it is not needed to hold any particular position in teaching/research to have access to a seat in this management body. The following figure shows the grade profile by sex in academic and professional services staff, suggesting that at higher levels (from level J onwards) there is an inversion and men become over-represented. In an institution where women are on the whole slightly above half of all staff, this suggests that there are still issues related to women’s access to leadership and decision-making positions.

With regard to qualitative information, there is a concern about whether OBU is facing gendered patterns of inclusion when appointing new leaders. There is a risk of assigning roles in softer areas to women (HR, Students experience, Staff Experience).

If we analyze its academic background, profiles in top positions come from a more scientific background (where gender studies are not sufficiently tackled neither in the curricula nor the research lines)) instead of being people with a cultural studies background. This, in thoughts of an OBU leader, “increases, the risk of not understanding the language of addressing gender inequality”.

As a last area of improvement, OBU also has a lack of clear, visible roles of successful women in leadership positions for aspiring, young women entering academia (particularly clarifying is the quotation from an interview with a leader at OBU: *You can’t be what you can’t see*).

4. Sabanci University - SU

Sabancı University also faces gender imbalance, both in so some faculties’ bodies and highest decision-making structures (being this last one the widest one). In fact, if we attend to statistics, at University level, in all the bodies with the exception of the Director’s level, the presence of women is less than 40 per cent, as the following table shows:

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	Women	Men
Board of Trustees	33%	67%
President and Vice-Presidents	0%	100%
Deans	33%	67%
Vice-Deans	33%	67%
Directors	63%	37%
University Academic Council	10%	90%
Secretary General	0%	100%
University Executive Board	42%	58%

In order to explain the imbalances in decision-making structures, the following table presents at the numbers of men and women in academic staff (Table 2),

	Women	Men
Professor	20%	80%
Associate Professor	24%	76%
Assistant Professor	44%	56%
Instructor PhD	46%	54%
Instructor	64%	36%
Research Assistant	65%	35%

It can be seen a striking decrease in women’s numbers as they go up the career ladder. While the numbers of women are twice the size of men among Research and Teaching Assistants and among adjunct instructors (*PhD holders without an academic title*), numbers start dropping in academic title holders going down as low as % 20 among professors. This suggests that it is not only a leadership issue, but also career progression should also be tackled at SU.

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No quotas or other affirmative policies are applied or considered by the administration. However, some informal practices are being carried out in the appointment processes, such as making sure that all committees in the Research and Graduate Policies Directorate have women.

In their assessment, SU also identified several informal factors limiting selection for management bodies and committees:

- Even distribution of the workload: assuring that not the same people take part in all the commissions or management activities.
- Preference for Turkish-speaking candidates: unconsciously, there is a preference for Turkish speakers, as they state that the conversation in the bodies is more fluid.

Decision-making processes are seen as not so transparent and inclusive, particularly due to the fact that the selection criteria are not public.

Finally, several aspects should be highlighted from the qualitative data gathering. The first one is a concern expressed by some women about the negative impact of exclusive man leadership style, as they believe the traits of women are different and complementary to the ones of men.

Furthermore, there is an increasing concern about women preventing other women from rising to high positions.

Lastly, women value more positively affirmative measures than men. The interviewed men, generally speaking, do not see a structural problem regarding women access to leadership positions and their representation in management bodies.

5. Estonian Research Council - ETAg

ETAg also experienced gender imbalances in women representation in top positions. This is currently solved due to a personal boost from the Director General of ETAg for the appointment of women within the bodies in which they are more underrepresented (i.e. the Evaluation Committee, the expert panels and the remote peer reviews). The Evaluation Committee, one of the highest decision-making bodies of ETAg, has followed this path:

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On its side, the expert panels created by ETAg to evaluate research proposals, are well-balanced, with some exceptions:

	Women	Men
Humanities and the Arts	82%	18%
Social Sciences	67%	33%
Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences	50%	50%
Medical and Health Sciences	64%	36%
Engineering and Technology	0%	100%
Natural Sciences	31%	69%

In order to give some context to these data, the proportion of researchers in Estonia (source: Statistics Estonia, 2019) by research field is presented:

	Women	Men
Humanities and the Arts	60%	40%
Social Sciences	62%	38%

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Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences	56%	44%
Medical and Health Sciences	71%	29%
Engineering and Technology	29%	71%
Natural Sciences	36%	64%

Comparing this data with the share of researchers in Estonia by research field, we can appreciate that, although the similar trend is followed, the nominations for the expert panels has some differences that would be interesting to explore.

ETAg, and the Estonian society as a whole, also displays a high resistance to quotas as a positive affirmative measure (in particular, it is stated that *Estonian society is not prepared for quotas*). Linked to that resistance, several people interviewed have the perception that time will solve the situations of imbalance, due to the eventual incorporation of women to the top positions in science (which is the pool of people from which the institution selects its members).

Last thing we have to take into consideration is the perception of a lack of training about unconscious biases regarding gender issues. However, people inside the institution do not see this topic as a priority, as they recognize that there are other high importance topics to talk about and limited resources to deal with all of them.

6. University of Deusto - UDEUSTO

UDEUSTO has to pay attention to several issues regarding leadership and decision-making. First, top positions are dominated by men. The following table shows the composition of the main top management bodies:

	Women	Men
Board of Governors	18%	81%
Board of Directors	25%	75%
Rectorate	33%	67%
Academic Council	35%	65%

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Women have more presence in middle management, particularly all the Dean's teams and departments head, in which their participation accounts for 50-60% in most of the faculties.

Women with permanent positions at UDEUSTO (who are eligible for the top management bodies) represents a 62% of the full professors and 51% of the chairs. Contrasting these proportions with their presence in top management bodies, it can be concluded that gender issues in leadership exist at UDEUSTO.

However, there is little perception of inequality in the composition of the management bodies when talking to the actual members of the top management. In fact, most of them displayed a high resistance to quotas and other affirmative measures arguing a struggle between meritocracy and gender balance).

Another area of improvement is the lack of perception of additional barriers for women in the access to leadership positions.

Regarding the leadership model of the university, it generally remains very unattractive to women as these positions bring in additional tasks and workload. All leaders, women or men, identify more difficulties to reconcile work and personal life, but the issue is worst for women because in most cases they also have to deal with family matters.

Finally, another area of work for UDEUSTO is the fostering of personal abilities of women, as a lack of awareness of the personal capacities to access to leadership positions has been identified. In particular, an impostor syndrome in some women belonging to the management bodies, who are not fully aware of the personal qualities that justify their appointment.

3. Design of specific trainings about leadership

Based on the different issues on the field of leadership identified for each institution, the purpose of this section is to develop a set of training activities in order to target directly the identified weaknesses.

Three different types of activities will be developed, with different audiences and formats:

- **Workshops in the context of the Pairing Events:** The aim of these workshops is to give the members of the GEP implementing institutions attending Pairing Events some insights about different topics related to the gender perspective in leadership, with a particular focus in the practical aspects a HEI may need to develop specific gender sensitive leadership and governance. These workshops will include preferably some participatory technique, in which the contents explained, targeting the specificities of each institution. The facilitation of these training modules will be in hands of WP5 coordinator at UDEUSTO.

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- **Online Webinars:** The online webinars are intended to be events in which the topics regarding leadership can be addressed in a more general way, targeting a larger audience. The aim is to reach most of the members of middle and top management leaders of GEP implementing partners, so that they can benefit from the knowledge and experience shared among the members of the consortium. Furthermore, in order to look for synergies with sister projects, a specific webinar may be organized in partnership with the GE-Academy. This will be a unique opportunity to bring together leaders of different backgrounds and projects to create a learning community based on the experience of the different actors participating in both projects.
- **Two-day Leadership Programme:** This leadership programme will be a complement to all the actions that will be designed and delivered in WP5. The programme puts its focus on women in middle management and intends to give them support in the progression of their careers. For this purpose, the facilitators will devote two days in order to build their skills and core competences so that they can be conscious of the issues women face and hurdles they may encounter and empowered to advance on their path to top positions in research and academia.

Following this general overview of the different activities that will be delivered, we will now focus on the content that each of the formative activities is intended to cover.

3.1 Workshops in the context of Pairing Events

1. Session 1: General overview of Gender in Leadership

The first session of the leadership workshops took place in the Pairing Event that was hosted by OBU in M6. In this session, a general overview of the consequences of women's limited representation in leadership was given. The following areas were covered: Gender in management, communication, WLB, salary wages and other rewards, cultural values and leader's awareness.

To end the session, the teams of each institution made a reflection about the strengths and resistances of their organization regarding the different areas that had been covered. Afterwards, these findings were shared with the entire group to find common challenges and take-home messages.

2. Session 2: Flows of Decision-Making at GEP implementing partners

The second session took place during the Pairing Event in IGOT-UL in M11. This session focused on the flows of decision-making in higher education institutions. The aim was to provide some concepts regarding the importance of having decision-making processes that do not create

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barriers for the advancement of women in HEIs and research institutions. In this sense, the topics covered included the different types of decision-making processes (structured vs. unstructured), the gender biases, and the consequences.

Then, to turn the concepts into practice, we asked the different teams to design and share with the group a typical decision-making process of a Dean's appointment in their institution (or any top management position in the case of RFOs), putting particular emphasis on the biases that each phase of the process may encounter.

3. Session 3: Gender Biases in Decision-Making

Following the line set by the previous workshops, in the Pairing Visit of M18 at UL, we propose to go deeper into the gender biases in decision-making processes. In particular, we will analyze the different kind of biases (criteria and performance of the process) and find possible measures that can be implemented in the different processes in which gender and leadership positions are present (e.g. selection and promotion processes) in order to minimize these biases.

For these purposes, an activity complementary to the one performed in Lisbon will be created, but with the focus in looking for improvements of the processes rather than identifying the gender biases so both sessions complement each other without overlapping.

4. Session 4: Gender Stereotypes

In the first workshop of the series, we addressed gender stereotypes as one of the factors contributing to the barriers in the access of women to leadership positions. Therefore, in M23 at SU we will go deeper in this particular factor. The session will try to give light to the different stereotypes that contributes to the so-called *gender-role incongruity* that prevents women from reaching leadership positions. Stereotypes attributed to men and women and how can they turn into implicit gender biases are going to be the core content of the session. As before, some activity regarding this gender stereotypes will be performed in order to create awareness in the attendants and to provide inputs for a general discussion.

5. Session 5: Leadership Styles

We will continue with the same guiding thread (the *gender-role incongruity* in women) and give an approach of different existing leadership styles and the traits associated to each of them.

The session will be hosted by UDEUSTO in the M30 and its intention is to make the attendants think about the leadership style that is valued in each of the institutions. Furthermore, we will tackle the gender perspective in leadership styles by underlining the unique differences between the leadership styles of men and women in the workplace and the advantages and disadvantages of one and the other. The aim will be trying to boost a personal leadership style that incorporates nuances of both tendencies.

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6. Session 6: Wrap Up: Experiences about Leadership and Decision-Making in HEIs

ETAg will host the final session of this set of workshops in M35. As this session will take place during the GEP implementation period, it will be a good opportunity to wrap up the different actions in leadership that are being implemented and the difficulties that institutions are facing in order to tailor the session to address those specific topics.

3.2 Online webinars

During the Year 2 of the project, four online webinars are intended to be held in the context of WP5, one of them organized in collaboration with the GE-Academy project. Of these four webinars, two of them (including the one in collaboration with GE-Academy) will be open to general public and two of them restricted to GEARING-Roles GEP implementing partners. In any case, in all of them the participation of leaders of the GEP implementing partners is expected.

Regarding the content of the webinars, it responds to the needs identified by partners in the Institutional Assessments. Priority issues common to all institutions were: lack of awareness by senior management teams; resistances to implementation; and bias. Two will be closed, and two open. Partners will be asked to select one or two senior management leaders to participate in the webinar series (specifically Webinars 2 and 4)

In the first webinar (open) Maxime Forest will speak on bias and Lucy Ferguson will speak on resistances to gender equality in leadership and decision-making. The focus will be on key challenges faced, and how to overcome these. Participants will be made up of senior management representatives from each institution, consortium members, sister projects and the general public.

The second webinar (closed) follows up on Webinar 1. It will include the senior management teams of partner institutions, and allow for a more in-depth reflection on the issues discussed. The rationale is that participants will have some information on which to base their discussions. The webinar will be participatory in order to allow participants to reflect on bias and resistances in their own institutions and facilitated by Lucy Ferguson.

In the third webinar (open) two speakers will share their experiences as senior leaders in research and innovation. This will include challenges, resistances, biases and how these were addressed and overcome. Participants will be made up of consortium members, sister projects and the general public. Senior management representatives who participated in Webinars 1 and 2 will also be encouraged to participate.

The last webinar (closed) will follow up on the in-person training (Two-Day Leadership Programme, explained below), reflecting on the key lessons learned and how these have been put into practice since the training. In the final session of the training, participants will be asked to develop an Action Plan, which will be shared with the group. These Action Plans will form the basis for the content and approach of the webinar, allowing each institution to explore the issues

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in-depth. Participants will be made up of those who attended the training, plus further consortium members who were not able to attend in-person.

Alternatively, this webinar will serve as a preparatory session for the in-person training, should this need to be postponed.

3.3 Two-day Leadership Programme

YW (not WP5 Coordinators) will design and deliver the Leadership Programme. We define the following as learning objectives for the course.

At the end of the training, the participants should be able to:

- Critically assess stereotypical traits commonly associated with leaders, recognize stereotypical expectations and feel empowered to counter these;
- Recognize typical hurdles and institutional biases women may face, and find ways to circumvent or overcome those;
- Feel strengthened in their self-confidence and potential to be capable (future) leaders;
- Feel supported by peers who they can relate to.

In order to achieve these challenges, the participants in the programme need to be aware of the (possible) biases in the existing structures they could encounter in the access of women to top positions and to empower them to recognize and overcome them.

